

Plant regeneration toward transformation of several javanica rice cultivars

I.H. Slamet, A. Estiati, W. Rahayu, s. Hutajulu, S. Nugroho, Research and Development Centre for Biotechnology-Indonesian Institute of Science, Jl. Raya Bogor Km 46, Cibinong 16911, Indonesia

The successful culturing of rice in vitro strongly depends on the genotype and culture used (Cooley et al 1995). Most successful transformation work has involved japonica rice cultivars; only a few indica cultivars have so far been transformed. The competency of plant material to regenerate in vitro is a prerequisite for transgenic research. Here we describe plant regeneration studies from a range of indica and javanica rice cultivars.

We cultured scutella of mature rice seeds on three media compositions (Li et al 1993, Poonsapaya et al 1989, Abdullah et al 1986) for embryogenic callus induction. Regenerated calli were identified and proliferated for transformation experiments using *Agrobacterium* strain EHA 101 pIG121 Hm (Hiei et al 1994) or DNA coated microprojectile bombardment techniques.

Based on the results of preliminary embryogenesis studies of 45 rice cultivars on Linsmaier and Skoog medium (unpublished results), five indica cultivars (Cisadane, Dodokan, Gajah Mungkur, Maninjau, and Kelimutu) and 10 javanica cultivars (Gebang, Rajalele, Rajalele KA, Asemandi, Aselapan, Kencana Bali, Caping Gajah, Jalawara, Pandan Wangi, and Raja Imut) were selected.

Calli were induced from 50 mature seeds in three different solid media designated as IK1 (Li et al 1993), IK2 (Poonsapaya et al 1989), and IK3 (Abdullah et al 1986) and incubated at 28 °C in the dark for 30 d. At 4 wk, each callus of 3-5 mm diameter was numbered and divided into two parts. The first part was subcultured onto the original induction callus medium while

the second part was transferred onto a medium described by Poonsapaya (1989) (Linsmaier and Skoog basal medium, 0.5 mg IAA L⁻¹, 0.3 mg BAP L⁻¹, 3% sucrose) followed by subculturing plantlets onto Murashige and Skoog basal medium. Regenerated calli were identified and corresponding calli were proliferated on the induction media for transformation experiments.

Regenerable calli from rice cultivars Cisadane, Maninjau, Gajah Mungkur, and Gebang were bombarded with tungsten particles (0.5-1 mm diam) coated with plasmid pAHC 25 (Christensen et al 1992) using a particle inflow-helium gun (He pressure of 800 kPa, vacuum pressure -50 kPa) and selected on medium containing bialaphos. Regenerable calli from Caping Gajah, Rojolele KA, Jalawara, and Koshihikari (control) were infected with *Agrobacterium* strain EHA101 harboring pIG121Hm according to the method described by Hiei et al (1994).

Plasmid pAHC25 was provided by the United States Department of Agriculture and the *Agrobacterium* strain pIG121Hm was obtained from Nagoya University, Japan. Bombarded and infected calli were histochemically assayed for their GUS activity with assay buffer described by Rueb et al (1989).

The most regenerated plants from the 15 cultivars tested were obtained from indica cultivar Maninjau and javanica cultivars Rojolele KA, Caping Gajah, and Jencana Bali (Table 1). In general, the Linsmaier and Skoog basal medium with the addition of 6% coconut water and 2.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ (Poonsapaya et al 1989) combined with the plant regeneration medium gave more regenerated plants. However, different cultivars responded differently when they were cultured following the same plant regeneration medium scheme.

The experiment was repeated for the three most responsive varieties

Table 1. Number of regenerated plants of several indica and javanica cultivars on three callus induction media.^a

Cultivar	Callus induction medium		
	IK1 (no. of plants)	IK2 (no. of plants)	IK3 (no. of plants)
Kelimutu	0	9	4
Gajah Mungkur	3	10	0
Cisadane	5	9	2
Dodokan	0	0	0
Maninjau	0	70	0
Rojolele	0	10	0
Rojolele KA	8	59	0
Asemandi	0	3	0
Aselapan	1	0	0
Jalawara	5	0	0
Kencana Bali	5	24	24
Raja Imut	2	7	11
Gebang	9	0	0
Caping Gajah	9	8	41
Pandan Wangi	0	0	0

^aNumber of plants obtained from 50 seed scutella after 8-10 wk.

Table 2. Number of regenerated plants of selected indica and javanica cultivars on three callus induction media.

Cultivar	IK1 medium		IK2 medium		IK3 medium	
	(no. of plants)	(no. of plants seed ⁻¹)	(no. of plants)	(no. of plants seed ⁻¹)	(no. of plants)	(no. of plants seed ⁻¹)
Caping Gajah	35	1.70±0.15	24	0.48±0.14	39	0.18±0.24
Rojolele	13	0.33±0.13	5	0.10±0.06	95	0.19±0.28
Maninjau	0	0	9	0.26±0.11	7	0.18±0.09

^aNumber of plants obtained from 50 seed scutella after 4 wk.

(Table 2); data were recorded for plant regeneration after 4 wk.

We conclude that an efficient plant regeneration system has been obtained from embryogenic calli of javanica cultivars Rojolele KA and Caping Gajah despite earlier claims that javanicas are resistant to tissue culture.

Bialaphos-resistant calli expressing *gus-A* gene resulting from bombardment experiments were obtained from indica rice cultivars Gajah Mungkur and Maninjau (data not shown). Scoring of *gus* transient expression of rice calli infected with *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain EHA 101 (pIG121Hm) gave a high percentage of *gus* positive calli. We are now growing these calli on medium containing hygromycin to obtain stable transformed material.

Cited references

- Abdullah R, Cocking EC, Thompson JA. 1986. Efficient plant regeneration from rice protoplasts through somatic embryogenesis. *Bio/Technology* 4:1087-1090.
- Cooley J, Ford T, Christou P. 1995. Molecular and genetic characterization of elite transgenic rice plants produced by electric-discharge particle acceleration. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 90:97-104.
- Christensen AH, Sharrock RA, Quail PH. 1992. Maize polyubiquitin genes: structure, thermal perturbation of expression and transcript splicing, and promoter activity following transfer to protoplast by electroporation. *Plant Mol. Biol.* 18:675-689.
- Li LC, Qu R, de Kochko A, Gauquet C, Beachy RN. 1993. An improved rice transformation system using the biolistic method. *Plant Cell Rep.* 12:250-255.
- Murashige T, Skoog R. 1962. A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassay with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiol. Plant.* 15:473-497.
- Poonsapaya P, Nabors MW, Wright K, Vajrabhaya M. 1989. A comparison methods for callus culture and plant regeneration of RD25 rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in two laboratories. *Plant Cell Tissue Organ cult.* 16:175-186.
- Rueb S, Hensgens LAM. 1989. Improved histochemical staining for beta-D-glucuronidase activity in monocotyledonous plants. *Rice Genet. Newsl.* 6:168-169. ■
- T. Cauchy, Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD-CA), Centre français du riz, Mas du Sonnailler, Route de Gimeaux, F-13200 Arles, France; S. Pichot, CIRAD-CA, Biotrop-Gerdat Laboratory, BP 3035, F-31032 Montpellier Cedex, France; G. Clement, CIRAD-CA, Centre français du riz; H. Chair and E. Guiderdoni, CIRAD-CA, Biotrop-Gerdat Laboratory

Variation among plants, regenerated from microspore-derived cell suspension protoplasts of rice

Rice embryo and microspore-derived calli are suitable for establishing embryogenic cell suspensions from which protoplast preparations can be readily isolated, engineered, and regenerated to plants. In that aim, somaclonal variation should be minimized. However, ploidy, chromosomal, morphological, and molecular changes have been extensively reported in plants regenerated from embryo callus-cell suspension protoplasts and their progenies.

We recently reported variation in ploidy level among plants regenerated from microspore-derived, haploid cell suspension protoplasts of japonica rice cultivar Miara (Guiderdoni and Chair 1992), as well as a high frequency of agronomical changes in progenies of the diploid protoclines generated in that study (Mézenecv et al 1995). To determine whether the importance of this variation is related to the genotype rather than to our haploid protoplast-

to-diploid plant system, we conducted ploidy analyses and field evaluation among plants regenerated from haploid protoplasts of the temperate japonica cultivar Ariete, the top rice variety in Italy and France.

Flow cytometric analyses of nuclei isolated from protoplast preparations of two and three 4-mo-old cell suspensions established from microspore-derived calli of cultivars Miara and Ariete, respectively permitted detection of haploid nuclei in four suspensions and a mixture of haploid and diploid nuclei in two suspensions (Table 1). We later found ploidy to remain stable over culture periods of up to 18 mo in fully haploid cell suspensions, whereas the haploid to diploid cell ratio varied among suspension cells exhibiting two ploidy levels.

Protoplasts isolated from haploid suspensions yielded a majority of diploid plants whereas the majority of plants derived from suspensions consisting of both haploid and diploid cells exhibited ploidy levels superior or equal to 4n. Distribution of ploidy levels was similar among plants derived from haploid protoplasts of cultivars Miara and Ariete. This was consistent with our previous findings that attributed ploidy changes to early polyploidization events during protoplast culture (Guiderdoni and Chair 1992).

R1 progenies of 72 diploid plants derived from haploid protoplasts of variety Ariete (A4 cell suspension)

Table 1. Ploidy of plants regenerated from microspore-derived cell suspension protoplasts of cultivars Miara and Ariete.

Genotype	Cell suspension	Ploidy level at time of isolation	Samples analyzed (no.) ^a	Frequency of plants exhibiting a ploidy level of					
				n	2n	3n	4n	5n	≥6n
Miara	M1 ^b	n	422	2.1	59.9	12.6	24.4	0.9	0
	M2	n	65	1.5	60.2	21.5	13.8	0	3.0
	M3	n+2n	75	0	10.7	1.3	24.0	12.0	52.0
Ariete	A4 ^a	n	59	1.7	50.9	13.5	30.5	3.4	0
	A4 ^a	n	113	2.5	59.5	17.1	14.4	1.0	5.5
	A6	n	57	1.8	43.8	3.5	38.6	5.3	7
	A7	n+2n	60	10.0	15.0	1.7	28.3	1.7	43.3
Thaibonnet	TB1 ^c	2n	74	0	74.3	2.7	18.9	1.4	2.7

^aResults of two experiments, 4 and 10 mo after initiation of the cell suspension. ^bMean data from 4 experiments (from Guiderdoni and Chair 1992). ^cSeed embryo-callus-derived cell suspension (diploid control).